

Why do we observe many subsistence farmers or low-wage workers in less developed countries? What is the role of credit markets in this phenomenon? Do you think that improving credit access can solve the problem of occupational choice? Why do you think so?

(ES30035: Coursework)

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SECTION A

Q5.

1. Introduction

A striking characteristic of the global economy is the wide income inequality observed across nations. For instance, in 2022, per capita incomes in Burundi and the Central African Republic stood at \$240 and \$480 respectively, with more than 80% of their populations relying on subsistence farming or low-wage work for income (World Bank, 2023). In stark contrast, the United States boasted a per capita income of \$76,370, with majority of the population working in either the industrial or services sectors. Despite some improvement in income inequality in recent decades, certain countries, geographical regions, and individuals continue to remain poor year after year.

One of the reasons for this is the existence of poverty traps. These can be described as a set of self-reinforcing mechanisms wherein individuals or economies that start poor, remain poor (Kraay and McKenzie, 2014). These can exist both at a macro and micro level and are driven by a plethora of factors that are external to a country or individual. This essay delves into a micro-level perspective on poverty traps, specifically exploring the impacts of credit market imperfections on occupational choice and incomes in less-developed countries. The analysis begins by presenting a model illustrating how credit markets influence the occupational choice of individuals. It demonstrates how individuals from impoverished households are often excluded from credit markets, despite being creditworthy, due to a lack of collateral. Consequently, they are unable to enter profitable occupation and are compelled into subsistence farming or low-wage work. The resulting low levels of wealth are perpetuated across generations, creating a cycle of persistent poverty. Building upon the insights derived from the model, the essay subsequently explores policy interventions aimed at improving credit access and assesses their effectiveness in solving the problem of occupational choice.

2. The model

2.1. Model Setup

To demonstrate how credit markets impact occupational choice, we examine a simplified economy represented by generations of successive agents who live for one period each and are linked by an inheritance.

At the start of a period, each agent is endowed with 1 unit of labor and an initial wealth (Z). Labor is homogenous to all agents and the only source of heterogeneity is their inherited wealth. Agents supply their labor to earn an income (Y) and allocate their inherited wealth to maximize end of period wealth. The total income earned is then divided between consumption and bequest to the next generation.

2.2. Occupations

The model considers three occupations:

(a) Subsistence producer: Utilizes labor to produce some fixed amount (S) and places inherited wealth in the bank which earns an interest (rZ).

$$Y^S = s + (1 + r)Z \quad (1)$$

(b) Industrial Worker: Utilizes labor to work for an entrepreneur and earns a competitive wage (w) determined by the labor market. Inherited wealth is again placed in the bank and earns an interest.

$$Y^W = w + (1 + r)Z \quad (2)$$

(c) Entrepreneur: Invests an amount (I) to start a firm. To make this investment, the entrepreneur borrows money via the credit market and will have to pay this back with interest. They use their inherited wealth as collateral. Additionally, to operate the firm, they hire m industrial workers and pays them the competitive wage rate, w to produce output q . Inherited wealth is again put in the bank and earns an interest.

$$\begin{aligned} Y^E &= q - mw - I(1 + r) + (1 + r)Z \\ &= q - mw - (1 + r)(I - Z) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In the model we assume

$$\begin{aligned} q - ms - (1 + r)(I - Z) &> s + (1 + r)Z \\ &= q - ms - (1 + r)I > S \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

When wages are equal to the subsistence output, being an entrepreneur is better than being an industrial worker.

2.3. Credit markets

Credit markets involve two participants: the lender and the borrower. Lenders decide whether to grant a loan, while borrowers determine if they repay it. A third-party enforcer intervenes if the borrower defaults. Imperfections, such as asymmetric information and enforcement problems, hinder the efficient allocation of credit.

Lenders often lack full information about borrowers, creating uncertainty about their credit worthiness. This relates to a borrower's ability to pay determined by their credit history and productive incentives as well as their willingness to repay. Enforcement of loan contracts is also imperfect, and not all defaulting agents face consequences. To mitigate risk, lenders limit borrowing and require collateral which can be seized in the event of a default. This results in credit rationing. If an individual's wealth falls below a certain level, they would not get a loan no matter how high the interest rate they offer.

The credit market can be modelled as follows. In the event of a default, the probability of an entrepreneur being arrested is λ . In arrested, they lose their profits and wealth and face a fine (F); otherwise, they only lose their collateral.

Equation 5 below, shows that if the income when repaying the loan (RHS) is greater than the expected income when defaulting (LHS), the entrepreneur will pay back the loan.

$$q - mw - (1 + r)(I - Z) > (1 - \lambda)(q - mw) + \lambda(-F) \quad (5)$$

Rearranging this from the lender perspective, we can find the initial wealth required to receive a loan

$$\begin{aligned} (1 + r)(I - Z) &\leq (q - mw) - (1 - \lambda)(q - mw) + \lambda(F) \\ &= (1 + r)(I - Z) \leq \lambda(q - mw + F) \\ &= (1 + r)(I - Z) \leq \lambda(q - mw + F) \\ &= Z \geq I - \frac{\lambda(q - mw + F)}{1 + r} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Banks only advance loans to individual whose initial wealth is “high enough”. If an individual’s wealth is lower than this threshold, they are unable to become entrepreneurs and are forced into subsistence farming or industrial work. This is the case in less developed countries, where majority of individuals lack fixed assets that serve as collateral. This is further amplified by poorly developed property rights, making appropriating collateral in the event of default difficult (Besley, 1994).

Additionally, when the cost of punishment and the probability of being arrested is low, the threshold increases. In less-developed countries, financial markets are often underdeveloped with excessively lenient loan enforcement policies, weak courts, and weak debt-collection rights which make it harder to access credit (Rosenthal & Bolton, 2005).

1.4 Labor markets:

The credit market threshold and initial wealth distributions in each period determines the number of people that can access credit and hence the number entrepreneurs. The rest opt for subsistence farming or industrial work. These occupational decisions impact the supply and demand for labor determining the equilibrium wage in the labor market.

The supply curve is as follows: when $w < s$, there is no incentive for labor market participation and individuals choose subsistence farming. At $w = s$, there is a jump in labor supply as individuals become indifferent between subsistence and wage employment. Labor supply increases as wages increase. Equation 6 illustrates this because when wages rise, the credit access threshold increases and occupational choice shifts from entrepreneurship to wage employment. This continues until $w = \bar{w}$ where profit from running a business equals labor income, rendering individuals indifferent between being workers and entrepreneurs. As $w > \bar{w}$, labor income is higher than business profit and there are no entrepreneurs.

Turning to labor demand: As $w > \bar{w}$, there is no labor demand as nobody wants to be an entrepreneur. As $w = \bar{w}$, there is a jump in labor demand as people enter entrepreneurship. Labor demand steadily rises for lower wages due to increased credit access. Combining both curves reveals the equilibrium wage rate, w^* .

Figure 1

In less developed countries, wealth distributions are highly unequal and only a few meet the credit access threshold. There is therefore a substantial labor supply at any wage exceeding s and minimal demand at wages below \bar{w} , resulting in a low equilibrium wage rate at $s = w^*$ as shown below.

Figure 2

When $s = w^*$, workers are indifferent between subsistence farming and industrial work. Since demand is lower than supply, those able to become industrial workers will do so and the rest fall into subsistence farming. Workers with low Z endure low wages while a select few profit from this, exacerbating inequality.

The prevailing wage impacts an individual's lifetime income and subsequent bequests to the next generation. Since majority of households are stuck with low wages, their offspring inherit little to no wealth and find themselves in a similar position to their parents in the next period. Households starting off poor are likely to endure poverty across generations.

3. Improving access to credit

In many developing countries, more than half the population lack access to credit services. For example, in Sub Saharan Africa, less than one in five households can access credit (Luan & Bauer, 2016). Apart from collateral constraints and credit market imperfections, other factors such as geographical distance can hinder credit access especially in rural areas. Whilst Spain has 96 branches per 100,000 people, Ethiopia has less than one (Beck et al., 2009). Unsurprisingly, countries with denser branch networks have a higher share of households with financial accounts. The documentation requirements for account opening pose an additional hurdle. Financial institutions typically demand identification documents, such as pay-slips, or proofs of residence. However, in low-income countries, especially where formal employment is scarce, individuals often lack such documentation. Limited education also impedes their ability to complete loan applications, and the small number of transactions they are likely to undertake discourage loan officers from assisting them (Beck et al., 2009).

Modern development theories increasingly emphasize the role of improving credit access in solving the problem of occupational choice and alleviating poverty. Their objective is to ease credit constraints for poor households, enabling them to secure capital needed to initiate businesses or engage in other income generating activities. There are many ways in which this can be achieved. One way is to strengthen the enforcement capacity of lenders to increase the probability of borrowers being caught when they default as and increasing the fines imposed when this occurs. This reduces the threshold required to access credit. Additionally, providing incentives for entrepreneurship such as offering subsidies or tax reliefs can reduce investment size and increase potential income thereby lowering the credit threshold.

Micro-credit programs have also gained in popularity as a way to improve credit access. These programs aim to eliminate the collateral constraints for poor households by providing them with small loans to facilitate self-employment. Despite its theoretical benefits, little empirical evidence has been recorded on its impacts. The uncertainty stems from methodological difficulties in evaluating the impact on participating and non-participating households, without adequately accounting for other unobservable differences.

One study has attempted to quantify the income and employment effects of microcredit in Bangladesh. This is the case of Grameen bank, a successful microcredit program renowned for its group-based lending approach. In this model, credit is provided to individuals in groups, and default by one member is taken as default by the rest. It therefore leverages peer pressure to ensure loan repayment rather than using collateral.

Below are the results from the study. It shows the aggregate effects of microcredit using regression analysis in villages which had access to Grameen Bank services.

Explanatory variable	Log of average of households' employment hours per month						
	Farm employment			Non-farm employment			
	Self-employment	Wage employment	Total of farm employment	Self-employment	Wage employment	Total of non-farm employment	Total of farm and non-farm employment
Village has Grameen Bank?	0.109 (1.446)	-0.394 (-2.175)	-0.040 (-0.477)	0.511 (2.631)	-0.007 (-0.046)	0.197 (2.012)	0.068 (2.387)
Village has BRAC?	-0.312	-0.832	-0.465	0.144	0.423	0.124	-0.112

Figure 3 (Khandker et al., 1998)

Figure 3 illustrates that post implementation, self-employment increased in both the non-farm and farm sector by 51.1% and 10.9%. Additionally, wage employment in both sectors decreased, indicating a shift in preference for self-employment.

Explanatory variable	Log of average of households' annual income in taka						
	Farm employment			Non-farm employment			
	Self-employment	Wage employment	Total of farm employment	Self-employment	Wage employment	Total of non-farm employment	Total of farm and non-farm employment
Village has Grameen Bank?	0.081 (0.185)	-0.645 (-2.409)	0.003 (0.017)	2.419 (2.432)	0.374 (0.503)	1.503 (1.593)	0.294 (1.861)
Village has BRAC?	0.211 (0.479)	-0.975 (-2.940)	-0.068 (-0.354)	0.278 (0.278)	2.280 (2.923)	1.786 (1.966)	0.327 (2.137)

Figure 4 (Khandker et al., 1998)

Additionally, income from self-employment saw a substantial increase of 241% in the non-farm sector and 8.1% in the farm sector, suggesting that programme participants effectively utilized their labour to generate higher incomes in their own businesses compared to non-participants. For instance, improved credit access can enable farmers to adopt modern agricultural practices, leading to increased productivity and profitability. Similarly, it can allow individuals to explore entrepreneurial ventures beyond agriculture, contributing to economic diversification especially for women.

Grameen Bank's credit programme also induced a 13.5% increase in the village-level wage rate. The mechanism is shown below. The fall in wage employment due to more individuals choosing self-employment led to a leftward shift in labour supply and hence higher wages.

Figure 5

This however was not associated with an increase in demand for labour according to the study which would have further increased wage levels (Khandker et al., 1998). Individuals choosing self-employment, were not increasing labour demand. The extent of the wage increase therefore depends on the type of non-farm activities that microcredit finances and their growth/productivity potentials. Grameen Bank’s interventions boosted self-employment low profit ventures which did not increase demand for labour. To reach an equilibrium which has a higher number of entrepreneurs and industrial workers as well as a higher wage rate, a rightward shift in demand is needed. This will reduce the significance of subsistence farming and improve incomes leading to a reduction in poverty.

Figure 6

Technological advancements that increase productivity are therefore needed to achieve substantial poverty reduction in addition to encouraging self-employment. Unless such a transformation occurs, gains from this policy will not be fully realized. One shot intervention such as “big push” that implements coordinated investments in rural non-farm sectors can help economies reach a high tech and high wage equilibrium. Additionally, policies that improve the business environment and improve linkages to urban markets can further enhance efforts to expand these sectors.

While improving credit access provides an opportunity to improve occupational choice, it may not always be used effectively. In the case of Grameen Bank, only 45 per cent of eligible households participated in the micro-credit programme indicating a low of demand for credit (Khandker 1998). Engaging in self-employment requires a minimum level of entrepreneurial ability and confidence which very few people among the poor have (Pitt and

Khandker,1996). Limited education additionally reduces their chances of success, and behavioural biases such as myopia and lack of aspirations, further hinder their ability to capitalize on this opportunity (Dalton, Ghosal and Mani, 2015). To overcome these challenges, supplementary policies will need to be implemented in addition to improving credit access.

Another prominent microcredit program in Bangladesh called BRAC was implemented around the same time as Grameen Bank however their emphasis was more on human capital development, and they delivered various training programmes including financial literacy and skills development in addition to providing credit. Repeat borrowers from BRAC demonstrated higher returns to capital compared to Grameen Bank, highlighting the effectiveness of their programme (Khandker 1998). These findings suggest that for greater effectiveness, microcredit programs may benefit from incorporating ancillary services for poor and unskilled borrowers.

Finally, receiving credit may not always result in improved occupational choice. In South Africa, microfinance proved ineffective as 94% of the loans issued were allocated to satisfy basic needs (Hickel, 2017). Poor individuals, facing malnutrition and limited access to healthcare and education, may use credit to meet essential needs, potentially leading to debt traps. Supplementing conditional cash transfer programs with microcredit initiatives will allow individuals to meet their subsistence needs whilst also stimulating additional demand for goods that support small businesses.

4. Conclusion

In less-developed countries, limited credit access constrains occupational choices, pushing impoverished individuals into subsistence farming or low-wage work. This has dynamic effects that perpetuate poverty across generations. Enhanced credit access enables individuals to start their own businesses, positively impacting self-employment and income. It also has indirect effects on the economy through increased jobs and wages thereby reducing poverty. However, for credit policies to make a substantial difference in terms of breaking the poverty cycle and changing the growth trajectory of economies, it will need to be supplemented by other policy intervention such as “big push”, cash transfers and human capital development initiatives.

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Citations

- Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A. and Honohan, P. (2009) 'Access to financial services: Measurement, impact, and policies', *The World Bank Research Observer*, 24(1), pp. 119–145. doi:10.1093/wbro/lkn008.
- Besley, T. (1994) 'How do market failures justify interventions in rural credit markets?', *The World Bank Research Observer*, 9(1), pp. 27–47. doi:10.1093/wbro/9.1.27.
- Dalton, P.S., Ghosal, S. and Mani, A. (2015). Poverty and Aspirations Failure. *The Economic Journal*, 126(590), pp.165–188. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/eoj.12210>.
- Hickel, J. (2017). *The microfinance delusion: who really wins?* [online] the Guardian. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development-professionals-network/2015/jun/10/the-microfinance-delusion-who-really-wins>.
- Khandker, Shahidur R., 1998, *Fighting Poverty with Microcredit: Experience from Bangladesh*, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Khandker, S.R., Samad, H.A. and Khan, Z.H. (1998) 'Income and employment effects of micro-credit programmes: Village-level evidence from Bangladesh', *Journal of Development Studies*, 35(2), pp. 96–124. doi:10.1080/00220389808422566.
- Kraay, A. and McKenzie, D. (2014) 'Do poverty traps exist? assessing the evidence', *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 28(3), pp. 127–148. doi:10.1257/jep.28.3.127.
- LandLinks. (2016). *Central African Republic | LandLinks*. [online] Available at: <https://www.landlinks.org/country-profile/central-african-republic/>.
- Luan, D.X. and Bauer, S. (2016) 'Does credit access affect household income homogeneously across different groups of credit recipients? evidence from rural Vietnam', *Journal of Rural Studies*, 47, pp. 186–203. doi:10.1016/j.jrurstud.2016.08.001.
- Pitt, Mark M. and Shahidur R. Khandker, 1996, 'Household and Intrahousehold Impacts of the Grameen Bank and Similar Targeted Credit Programs in Bangladesh', *World Bank Discussion Papers*, No.320, Washington, DC.
- Ripple Effect. (n.d.). *Burundi*. [online] Available at: <https://rippleeffect.org/about/where-we-work/burundi> [Accessed 14 Dec. 2023].
- Rosenthal, H. and Bolton, P. (2005) *Credit markets for the poor*. New York: Russell Sage.
- World Bank (2023) GNI per capita, Atlas method (current US\$), World Bank Open Data. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GNP.PCAP.CD> (Accessed: 03 December 2023).